

Supplementary Table 5 Associations between different autoantibodies and PTPN22

polymorphism, in anti-CCP2-negative RA

Subgroup	Exposure		OR (95% CI)^a	OR (95% CI)^b
	<i>PTPN22-</i>	<i>PTPN22+</i>		
Controls	2202	595	1.0 (ref)	1.0 (ref)
ACPA-	370	141	1.43 (1.15-1.77)	1.42 (1.15-1.76)
ACPA+	221	81	1.36 (1.04-1.79)	1.38 (1.05-1.80)
RF-	406	145	1.33 (1.08-1.65)	1.34 (1.08-1.65)
RF+	185	77	1.55 (1.17-2.06)	1.55 (1.17-2.06)
other Ab-	404	154	1.42 (1.16-1.75)	1.43 (1.16-1.76)
other Ab+	187	68	1.35 (1.01-1.81)	1.34 (1.00-1.80)
any Ab-	176	71	1.51 (1.13-2.02)	1.51 (1.13-2.02)
any Ab+	410	148	1.36 (1.10-1.67)	1.36 (1.10-1.68)

Odds ratios were adjusted for ^a age, gender, residential area, and ^b SE and smoking. ACPA = any ACPA fine-specificity; RF = IgM and/or IgG and/or IgA RF; other Ab = any other autoantibody; any Ab = ACPA and/or RF and/or other autoantibody.